

THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC VALUE OF RCAAP

Launched in 2008, RCAAP is Portugal's national repositories network aggregating and sharing scientific content from institutions across all fields

Free and global access to **full-text documents and metadata**, with minimal restrictions (e.g. embargoes)

Users mainly from Portugal (96%) and Portuguese-speaking countries

Free institutional repository hosting service with flexible customisation and integration options

Users typically from **academia and other higher education institutions (88%)**

Extra support for institutions: from **journal & data hosting, to usage statistics, and training services**

Broad use across **scientific disciplines**

MAXIMISING VALUE THROUGH OPEN SHARED INFRASTRUCTURE

Net gain: Benefits are higher than costs

RCAAP operates on a collaborative model, relying on staff contributions from participating institutions (85% of total resources).

Average annual costs (2006–2026):
€200,000

Benefits come from shared hosting infrastructure, pooled expert resources, and reduced duplication of efforts

Average annual benefits (2006–2026):
€285,000

ENHANCING ACCESS TO PORTUGUESE RESEARCH

Participating institutions grew from **14 to 121 since 2008**

Over **1 million documents** available

Access to **over 40% of Portuguese academic research**

Portal **usage has tripled** since 2008

Supported by **strong, regularly updated legal and policy frameworks**

RCAAP advances multiple SDGs by offering free access to scientific knowledge, with the greatest impact on **SDG 4, quality education and lifelong learning**, serving students as key users

IMPACT ON USERS IF RCAAP DID NOT EXIST

20% could not have carried out their work

39% would have faced reduced research quality

59% would not have used a paid alternative

Without RCAAP, fragmentation would likely have increased, significantly limiting the development of Institutional Repositories in Portugal

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